

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF COMPLEXES

Lanthanone(II)	Ligand	log β^0			$-\Delta G^{0*}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H^{0*}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^{0*} JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
		25°	35°	45°			
La	H ₂ BB	8.8	8.9	9.0	50.1	23.6	239.3
	H ₂ BE	8.1	8.3	8.3	46.0	36.3	267.2
Pr	H ₂ BB	9.2	9.4	9.5	52.5	31.7	273.4
	H ₂ BE	8.6	8.6	8.8	48.9	16.3	211.7
Nd	H ₂ BB	9.7	9.8	9.9	55.2	12.7	220.5
	H ₂ BE	8.9	9.0	9.2	50.9	17.3	221.4
Sm	H ₂ BB	10.0	10.2	10.3	57.2	27.2	274.0
	H ₂ BE	9.3	9.4	9.4	53.0	24.5	251.6
Gd	H ₂ BB	10.4	10.5	11.6	59.1	25.4	274.4
	H ₂ BE	9.6	9.7	9.8	54.6	23.6	253.9
Tb	H ₂ BB	10.7	10.9	11.0	65.1	29.0	305.5
	H ₂ BE	10.0	10.1	10.3	57.0	22.7	258.8
Dy	H ₂ BB	11.1	11.2	11.3	63.2	25.4	287.7
	H ₂ BE	10.4	10.6	10.8	59.4	31.8	296.1
Ho	H ₂ BB	11.4	11.5	11.6	64.8	25.4	292.8
	H ₂ BE	10.9	11.0	11.1	62.0	24.5	280.8
Er	H ₂ BB	11.7	11.8	11.9	66.5	27.2	204.2
	H ₂ BE	11.2	11.4	11.5	64.1	27.2	296.4

*At 25°.

References

1. D. J. HODGSON, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, 19, 173.
2. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
3. E. HÜCKEL, *Z. Phys.*, 1925, 26, 93.
4. H. HARNED and L. KAZANJIAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1912.

A New Heterogeneous Selective Ion Sensitive Electrode for Lead(II) Ions

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LEAD ion-selective membrane electrode based on electroactive material like precipitated silver sulphide—lead sulphide is known¹. Pungor *et al.*² observed that the electrode surface becomes depleted in lead sulphide, lead sulphate crystals being formed during chemical oxidation and lead oxide crystals during anodic oxidation. The application of various lead electrodes based on lead sulphide have been discussed³. A number of other electroactive materials like lead selenide⁴, lead telluride, lead diisobutyl dithiophosphate⁵, lead(IV) oxide⁶

etc. have been used for the preparation of lead(II) ion selective membrane electrodes. Linder *et al.*⁷ prepared a lead selective neutral carrier based liquid membrane electrode. In this paper we report a new electrode for lead(II) ions in which lead(II) complex of salicylaldoxime has been used as an electroactive material for the ion-selective membrane electrode.

Experimental

Preparation of membrane: Salicylaldoxime (~1 g) was dissolved in 95% ethanol (5 ml). It was then diluted to 100 ml by water and added to ammoniacal solution (pH > 9) of lead acetate to precipitate⁸ the yellow complex PbC₇H₈O₂N which was dried in air.

Lead salicylaldoxime complex (100 mg) was thoroughly mixed with Araldite (Ciba-Geigy) (100 mg) on Whatman's filter paper No. 42. The paste was uniformly spread on the filter paper and then dried in air for 24 h to obtain a membrane of 0.5 mm thickness. The membrane along with the filter paper was immersed in 1.0 M lead nitrate solution and then the adhering filter paper was peeled off.

Preparation of electrode: A piece of membrane was cut out and fixed at one end of a pyrex glass tube (o.d. 0.8 cm, i.d. 0.6 cm) with Araldite. The tube was filled with a solution (0.01 M) of lead nitrate and kept immersed in 0.01 M lead nitrate for 6 days and then for at least 1 h before use. A

saturated calomel electrode served for making electrical contact.

A Philips PR 9405 M pH meter was used along with a second saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E) as a reference and a salt bridge was used for electrode potential measurements. Measurements were made at $20 \pm 2^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

After conditioning of the electrode, the potentials for a series of standard solutions of lead nitrate were measured. A linear response was observed upto concentration $10^{-6}M$. The slope was found to be 25 mV/decade change in lead concentration. Below $1 \times 10^{-6}M$, a non-linear response was observed but the calibration curve could be utilised for determination of lead down to $1 \times 10^{-7}M$. Even with continuous use, the slope of the electrode remained constant up to eight weeks after which it decreased. However, a linear response was maintained even after three months.

To find the response time, the electrode was dipped in $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ lead nitrate solution and the potential was recorded at short intervals. A constant steady potential was reached within one minute. It required approximately 50–60 s for the potential to come within ± 1 mV of its final value.

Two sets of lead nitrate solutions were prepared, 0.1 and 0.01 M. pH of both the solutions was varied in the pH range 1–10 using either dilute nitric acid or a very dilute solution of sodium hydroxide. It was observed that the electrode potentials of both the sets of solutions remained unchanged in the pH range 2.0–8.0.

The selectivity coefficients $K_{Pb^{II}}^{Pot}$ for seven cations were determined by the mixed solution method⁹ and the values obtained are: Cd^{II} (1.0), Hg^{II} (1.0), Co^{II} (0.01), Ni^{II} (0.01), Ca^{II} (0.005), Cu^{II} (0.005) and Fe^{III} (3.11). Thus the electrode can be used for determination of Pb^{II} in presence of Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} ions.

Application: The electrode was used as an indicator electrode in the precipitation titration of lead nitrate with various anions like sulphate, chromate etc. Since lead sulphate formed is soluble so a partially non-aqueous medium ethanol-water (1:1) was used. A sharp change in the potential was observed at the equivalence point.

The estimation of the drug carbimazole involves the determination of sulphide which is subsequently converted into lead sulphide. Five tablets of drug were mixed with 1M KOH (50 ml) and heated at $250-80^\circ$ for 10 min. After cooling, sodium plumbite was added to obtain lead sulphide. The excess of lead in the solution was analysed by potentiometric titration with EDTA (0.01M) at pH 4.6 (acetate buffer) using the lead selective electrode as above.

References

1. H. HIRATA and K. DATE, *Anal. Chem.*, 1971, 43, 279.
2. E. PUNGOR, K. TOTI, G. NAGY and L. POLOS, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1983, 147, 23.
3. M. S. JOVANOVIC, M. DJIKANOVIC, B. D. VUCUROVIC and Z. ABRAMOVIC in "Ion-Selective Electrodes", ed. E. PUNGOR, Elsevier, New York, 1981, p. 257.
4. H. HIRATA and K. HIGASHIYAMA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1971, 57, 476.
5. E. A. MATEROVA, A. L. GREKOVICH and N. V. GABUZOVA, *Obem. Ionometry (Russ.)*, 1976, 1, 137.
6. D. MIDGLEY, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1984, 159, 63.
7. E. LINDER, K. TOTI and E. PUNGOR, *Anal. Chem.*, 1984, 56, 1127.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th ed., ELBS, London, 1978, p. 468.
9. G. J. MOODY and J. D. R. THOMAS in "Ion Selective Electrodes", ed. E. PUNGOR, Akademiai Kiado, Budapest, 1973, p. 97.

Dehydration-Rehydration Behaviour of Zirconium Hydroxide and Aluminium Hydroxide Coprecipitated Hydrogel

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WATER¹ is a very important constituent of the hydrogel structure. Various physicochemical properties of the hydrogel depend on the quantity and orientation of the water molecules. During heat treatment of zirconium and aluminium hydroxide hydrogel, the speed of dehydration of one is influenced by the other². Mitra and Roy³ studied the effect of heat treatment of the synthetic aluminosilicate hydrogel below 200° and found evidences of gel skeleton collapse at higher temperatures⁴⁻⁶. In the present investigation, equilibrium dehydration loss experiments on zirconium and aluminium hydroxide coprecipitated hydrogels were carried out up to 600° and the above heat treated samples were subjected to rehydration at various humidities in order to study the structural flexibilities of the above hydrogel with respect to orientation of water molecules.

Experimental

Coprecipitated hydrogels of zirconium and aluminium hydroxide were synthesised by following wet interaction process of 5% aqueous solutions of $Al(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$, $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ (E. Merck; 99% purity) and liquor ammonia at pH 9 at $30-2^\circ$. After proper ageing the gels were processed to remove impurities as reported earlier⁵. The molar ratios of $ZrO_2 : Al_2O_3$ in the composition were kept at 1:3, 1:2 and 1:1 respectively.